

THE ROLE OF INDEPENDENT STUDYING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TERMINOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF PHILOLOGY STUDENTS

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Abstract. *The article discusses one of the urgent tasks of the current higher education system - the formation of a specialist with professional and terminological competence. Opinions about independent education in the educational system, its role, place and importance in the educational process are presented. Information is presented on the organization of independent education in the credit-module system in higher education and the development of terminological competence in philology students through this process. Specific characteristics of independent work tasks are taken into account. The advantages of using the credit-module system in higher education are described and recommendations are given. By paying attention to independent education, the role and importance of philology students in the development of terminological competence is analyzed.*

Keywords: *independent education, independent work, terminological competence, professional competence, individual knowledge, credit education system, didactic task, creative activity, term, qualified specialist.*

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, when science and technology are rapidly developing, it is impossible to deliver all information only during the course of the lesson. Therefore, independent education has been introduced in higher education, and this process leads students to study outside the classroom, research, work on themselves, and students' creativity, independent study forms learning, thinking skills. Independent education - strengthening and enriching the knowledge, skills and competences of students of a higher educational institution under the guidance and supervision of a pedagogue, acquired in lectures, seminars and practical training in academic and specialized subjects, and by them new education aimed at ensuring independent acquisition of knowledge, skills, skills, preparing them to organize professional activities independently [1]

Today, preparation of philology students for creative thinking and creative development, development of independent thinking skills in them is the main requirement of the State Education Standard.

"60111400 - Requirements for the professional competencies of bachelors in the field of Uzbek language and literature" contains the professional competencies of bachelors, and in "General competencies"

- Mastering the skills of written and oral speech in the native language and one of the foreign languages in order to systematically and freely express one's thoughts in the native language, work with scientific texts, and give a public speech.

- Using methods, methods and means of obtaining, storing and processing information; the ability to work with global computer networks.

In the section of professional competences:

- Knowledge of various theories of teaching, education, development, ability to use educational programs at various stages of education;

- It is envisaged to regularly improve theoretical knowledge of the Uzbek language and literature, to learn the current issues of the native language and literary sciences, to be able to apply them in teaching activities and to be able to convey them to students [2].

Independent education is of particular importance in the development of given general and professional competencies.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

The issue of the importance of independent education in the higher education system is discussed in the research works of Sh. Muhammedov, N. Suyunov, G'. Toshmatov, Sh. Kokanboyeva [3, 4, 5, 6]. consideration of the work as an important source was studied in the scientific research of many researchers, including A.M.Altaitsev, A.A.Verbitsky, S.I.Vershinin, I.A.Zimnyaya, I.F.Isaeva, and others. [7,8,9,10,11].

There are some uncertainties regarding the definition of self-employment. In particular, R. M. Mickelson says that independent work should be done by students without anyone's help under the supervision of the teacher [12]. S.I.Zinoviyev defines independent work as independent education. In his opinion, the search for individual knowledge is a general feature of the university student's educational activity; states that "the independent training of a student, which is carried out in parallel with the educational process of the university in independent work, is an independent educational process" [13].

In the works of N.V.Solovova and O.Yu.Kalmikova, various modern forms and types of tasks are given for independent work of students. The authors classify the tasks according to the parameters of the didactic goal: acquiring knowledge, strengthening and systematizing knowledge, developing skills and competences. Authors include working with textbook texts, additional literature, normative and legal documents, audio and video recordings, professional and popular articles [14].

M.V.Bulanova-Toporkova found that in most countries of the world, students' independent work outside of class is taken in the ratio of 3.5:1 to classroom training. emphasizes that it contributes to the mastery of educational methods, becomes the main reserve or increasing the efficiency of training specialists [15]

Sh.Kokanboyeva, independent work in higher education "processing lecture texts, articles; development of diagrams, tables, dictionaries, puzzles, crosswords for systematization of educational material; completing test tasks; answers to control questions; interpreting, summarizing, reviewing the text; compilation of resources on the studied topic, including a list of electronic resources; work with computer programs and other tasks" is effective.[6]

O.Askarova says that it is important to do various independent tasks in training, to educate students, and independence is considered a personal quality, to prepare students for independent work, to make independent tasks understandable, to allocate enough time for independent work and to check the result of independent work. Independent work on the rules and definitions in the textbook: reading the rules and definitions in the textbook and distinguishing the factors related to them; analyze the factors collected according to the teacher's assignment and make conclusions; to selectively read some pages of the textbook and prepare a brief report on ways to use this knowledge in practice; rules, dividing definitions into logical parts and collecting material from the literature in addition to the terms within the scope of the studied topic; emphasizes comparing

the conclusions drawn by the teacher during the lecture, story, conversation with the rules and definitions in the textbook.[16]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Agreeing with the above opinion, it is necessary to say separately that the role of independent education in the formation of terminological competence in future philological specialists is incomparable. Thorough assimilation of the terms, definitions and rules learned in the lecture and practical training, bringing the terms into the range of independent work topics serves to increase professional and terminological competence.

In the credit education system, independent work of students is considered the main activity and is a unique educational activity of the student. It directs to independent completion of didactic tasks, interest in reading and increasing knowledge in a specific field of science. It is desirable that the content of the students' independent work should be related to the performance of practical tasks that allow them to develop logical thinking, creative activity, and a research approach to mastering the learning material. This process directly creates the ground for reading and learning terms related to the specialty, as well as mastering them thoroughly.

Usually, independent work of students includes independent work of the student under the guidance of the teacher, which is performed outside the classroom, together with the full independent activity of the student. In full-time undergraduate studies, the total number of hours of independent work of students is half of the volume of the subject, and almost half of it is allocated to independent work of the student under the guidance of the teacher. It is desirable that the volume of independent work of a student in external education should be 4/5 of the volume of the subject [17].

Thorough mastering of specialized terms is the basis for improving the quality and efficiency of education and training highly qualified personnel. To increase the quality and effectiveness of education, use of non-traditional methods of studying terms in science, modern methods, forms and tools of their teaching, game technologies, problem-based teaching, in particular, course work and independent work, plays an important role. Also, it is appropriate to provide philology students with the characteristics of subjects in the preparation of independent education in educational science programs. This includes studying the science terms given in the subject chapters and topics of textbooks and study guides, working on philological terms in the subject sections or topics of special literature, performing the student's educational and scientific research work. It is intended to direct the departments and topics of the sciences related to the in-depth study of philological terms. In general, the implementation of independent education in students requires an individual approach.

There are several types of independent education in the programs: 1) in-depth study of departments and topics related to students' educational and research work; 2) work with literature; 3) creative work; 4) abstracts and presentation preparation on some topics are mentioned, but how many topics a student can independently study and write an abstract on the topic, perform creative work and how to complete and evaluate them each semester? It would be appropriate if instructions were given, and if independent work topics were enriched with topics and tasks related to the thorough mastering of specialized terms.

The fact that the number of hours allocated to independent education in the model curricula of pedagogical higher education institutions that prepare pedagogical personnel in our country is equal to the hours of the auditorium indicates how important independent education is. In this

process, the number of hours allocated to the audience and independent study in the curriculum of bachelors shows that it is necessary to pay attention to independent study of subjects. Taking this into account, the issue of developing the terminological competence of philological students through independent education occupies an important place.

From the observations, it can be said that the effectiveness of independent work does not depend only on the department that teaches this subject, but on the pedagogical conditions created in the higher education institution, including the information resource center of higher education and a sufficient level of education in the library. The existence of educational and scientific literature depends on the provision of educational and terminological dictionaries related to science.

It is necessary to take into account the characteristics of certain forms of science, as well as the mastery level and ability of each student, when organizing the independent work of philological students. There are no works on the conditions for organizing independent works in solving the problems of increasing the role of philological students in modern education and the problems of developing their terminological competence. In our opinion, it is necessary to pay special attention to the teaching of science-related terms in each subject's curriculum, working curriculum, topics, and each of their plans, to teach students terms that are considered important in their professional activities. Thorough mastering of terms is the main factor in developing a qualified specialist. In this sense, teaching of terms for lectures, practical, seminar classes and subjects of independent education and independent work, providing detailed information about them, about the meaning and essence of the terms in science providing concepts is one of the important conditions for developing future philologist students' terminological competence and professional qualities.

It is necessary to pay serious attention to the topics of intermediate and current control, independent education in the subjects specified in the curriculum. In them, it is important to pay attention to such questions as the meaning, use, origin, etymology of scientific terms, synonyms, alternatives, scope of application.

It is necessary for every student to independently study, understand and independently master the task assigned to the subject. The most widely used method of organizing independent education is individual work of students. Students have an individual approach to knowledge, and existing knowledge is enriched with new knowledge. The main goal of independent education is to produce a mature, highly qualified, competitive specialist who is well-versed in his field and meets modern requirements.

It is important to develop terminological competences of future Uzbek language and literature teachers through independent education. In this regard, it is necessary to improve science programs, to make changes and additions to the subjects of independent education where necessary, and to pay attention to the study of terms of science. In particular, students of the first stage of Uzbek language and literature study the subject of "Uzbek folklore". In the curriculum of this subject, there are tasks aimed at mastering industry terms in a number of topics recommended for independent study. These are: "Explaining the difference and associative meanings of legends, proverbs and anecdotes in reflecting reality, comparative analysis of the genres of proverbs, riddles and riddles, paying attention to the original and figurative meanings of proverbs, harmonious and different meanings of riddles and riddles. "to dwell on the properties" was given to the students as an assignment. [2] It is gratifying that in these assignments there are topics and

assignments where attention should be paid to the genres of Uzbek folklore, the meaning of terms related to science. However, it is advisable to increase the number of independent educational topics aimed at learning such tasks and terms related to the science of Uzbek folklore.

CONCLUSION

In fact, the role of independent education is incomparable in the student becoming a mature expert in his field. Taking into account that the development of terminological competence in philological students, the careful mastering of specialized terms, the effective use of terms in educational and professional activities is the main task in the preparation of mature and competitive personnel, the independent work of the student in mastering specialized terms is of particular importance. Organization of independent education of philology students, in general, at a high level increases the effectiveness of education.

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